

Workshop: Collaborative practice to own your narrative and deconstruct the impostor phenomenon

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Introduction

Impostor Phenomenon, sometimes erroneously mentioned as Impostor Syndrome, is a widely recognized experience in which individuals fail to internalize their successes despite objective evidence. While initially (40 years ago), it was described among high-achieving White women ([Clance & Imes, 1978](#)), subsequent research examined the links of this phenomenon to various populations and outcomes. The coining of the Impostor Phenomenon term led to the boom of the self-help and personal development industry offering interventions, many lacking solid scientific basis.

Prevalence of the Impostor Phenomenon in the academic environment is sky-high (up to 95%), hitting all career stages - from undergraduate to faculty, both males and females, and damaging the minority groups ([Vaughn et al 2019](#), [Chakraverty, D. 2020](#), [Hewertson & Tissa 2022](#)).

Recent scientific and lay literature draw our attention to the need to contextualize the impostor phenomenon and highlight antecedents such as systemic discrimination - in contrast to previous trends to emphasize perfectionism or individual deficits as antecedents ([Feenstra et al, 2020](#), [New Yorker](#), [Harvard Business Review](#) publications).

Proposed interventions to overcome the Impostor Phenomenon often include theoretical workshops, training, coaching and therapy ([Zanchetta et al 2020](#), reviewed in [Bravata et al 2020](#)).

While evidence-based practice is often considered a gold standard in health care, there is a considerable gap between research and practice. Cross-disciplinary collaborations with practitioners have the potential to bridge that gap, exposing the value of practice-based evidence.

Discourses about the Impostor Phenomenon are often problem- and deficit-saturated narratives, whether it is speaking to the individual antecedents or systemic discrimination.

Narrative therapy approach to counseling and community work considers people as experts in their lives, views problems as separate from people, and assumes people have skills, competencies, beliefs, values, commitments and abilities that will assist them in reducing the influence of problems in their lives, and gain back a healthy sense of agency through

re-authoring conversations and other interventions. Moreover, narrative practice couples emotions with meaning, which is tightly linked to the culture, politics and ethics.

Erasmus+ project *Oediverse* combined knowledge and worked with the synergy of the modules Open Science, Mental Health and Storytelling in Science. This resulted among others in the workshop *Own Your Story*, targeting empowerment and raising the agency in academic narratives of researchers. The workshop deconstructs the notion and experience of failure and success on an individual level as well as from an academic and social perspective.

Purpose

Current submission arises as a fruit of continuous and cross-pollinating conversations between narrative practitioner-in-training with academic research background and immersive storytelling practitioner - designer of the *Own Your Story*, with experience in human-centered design thinking and co-creative collaborative processes. The concept of the proposed *exploratory workshop* that combines cognitive reflections and experiential practice was inspired by attending the 1st ReMO Conference in 2022. We believe that the virtual networking consortium and its related hybrid annual event would benefit from sessions like this one, especially when the conference is about Mental Health and Well-being of researchers.

Relying on the concept of agency, ownership of own “narrative” and design approach to social construction of preferred realities ([Freedman, J., & Combs, G. 1996](#)) and ideas of narrative practice ([M. White 2007](#), [Denborough 2018](#)), we will adapt the previously developed *Own Your Story* training on science communication and storytelling to address the Impostor Phenomenon in the STEM environment and academic context. We hope this would invite the participants to engage not only like researchers of the psychosocial phenomenon but as human beings, statistically at high risk of suffering from the same phenomenon.

Design

The initial training was designed to be 1 day long. For the purpose of the conference format during the 2nd ReMO conference, we aim to present a *one-hour duration session*, with immersive participation and collaborative dialogue about the individual, organizational and sociocultural components of the Impostor Phenomenon, with a focus on the intentional states of the participants. The exercises offered would involve exploration of preferred reality of the researcher (such as research culture, environment, societal and scientific impact) and underlying values, intentions, aspirations, later moving into behaviour and interaction, touching the obstacles and “Impostor Phenomenon” narratives at the end, which would allow us to collectively deconstruct the phenomenon.

Some parts of the exercises could be anonymously shared with the community as collective documents of deconstruction and evidence of counterposing the influence of the “Impostor Phenomenon”. The format is flexible for participation in person, online and hybrid versions.

Implications

Storytelling is a powerful tool when it comes to perceiving and shaping our reality through communication - whether personal or professional. *How do we become victims of the Impostor Phenomenon? How and why do we generate these stories often ourselves? How can we gain agency and change unhealthy narratives? How can we own our story instead of letting external narratives influence us to the extent of losing ownership? Who has the power? Who has the agency?* Those are questions to be answered.

The Impostor Phenomenon is often pathologized as a syndrome, although at its core it is a narrative phenomenon causing (the fear of) losing agency. Existing dominant power structures generate a distorted picture of reality, an inner narrative, that undermines a person's confidence in his or her abilities. The Impostor Phenomenon manifests itself in narratives of (the fear) of failure, in stories we tell each other and ourselves. We want to develop a narrative practice that makes us more aware of our conditioning, our reactivity to expectations, social and academic pressure and helps us deconstruct our relationship to the power structures encapsulated in the narratives of the Impostor Phenomenon.

The proposed workshop is an exploratory type of workshop, which aims to analyze certain ideas about Impostor Phenomenon, associated problems and working solutions collaboratively with the participants. Running the workshop would allow the authors to gather feedback from participants to deepen the collaboration and identify the next actions in development and scaling up of the training.

Resources

- [IO4 – Science Communication and Storytelling Training Day “OWN YOUR STORY”](#)
- [Collective Narrative Practice at the Dulwich Centre](#)

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